

WEBINAR REPORT

How to engage cities and regions in research collaboration for circularity?

Webinar recording link:

www.youtube.com/watch?v=t87BlmvowwY&t=5s

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Executive Summary

Cities and regions are major consumers of materials and resources. Yet, they are hubs for innovation and experimentation, where human capital is vibrant and capable of generating new ideas to contemporary challenges. Transforming cities and regions into circular ecosystems is one of those challenges. It demands new approaches to move from the current "take-make-dispose" model to a circular one where waste become material for other activities and resources maintain their value over time thanks to multiple transformations.

Being systemic for definition, circular transformations require collaboration among different stakeholders across cities and regions. Collaborations between researchers and urban or regional practitioners are fundamental to experimenting with new circular ideas and to scale them up into actions and initiative that are gradually capable of building circular transformations. Yet, several barriers limit effective research-practitioners' collaboration.

The workshop "How to engage cities and research collaboration for circularity" aimed to show successful examples of research-city collaborations in research projects.

Three Driving Urban Transitions (DUT)-funded projects shared their experiences.

- **ECLECTIC** described the importance of urban metabolism (UM) and presented the Coimbra Living Lab experience. Through research-city collaboration, Coimbra analyzed material flows and co-identified potential measures for resource optimization and circularity across key economic sectors to develop a circular economy action plan.
- **CORPUS** shared their collaborative approach to retrofitting public spaces in disadvantaged neighborhoods through participatory approaches and digital civic technologies in the cities of Turin (Italy) and Egaleo (Greece), exploring circular strategies for urban renewal.
- **CIRCULAR GRASSROOT** addressed barriers faced by grassroot initiatives in accessing production spaces. The Gothenburg (Sweden) subsidy case proved to be unsuitable for granting access to spaces due to the specific characteristics of grassroots organizations. New relations mechanisms between the local government and grassroot organizations will need to be established to effectively enhance the collaborative economy.

The second part of the workshop involved 58 representatives from public urban or regional governments, businesses, NGOs, research and academic institutions who discussed in **interactive sessions** how to strengthen their collaboration to support circular transformations. Key conditions identified include a **shared vision and common goals**, trust and transparency, and supportive policies. To this end, long-term commitment on circular transformations by city and regional governments through **continuous institutional support** and funding, trusted networks, effective communication are critical conditions for research-city collaborations to produce valuable results. This support can be strengthened and scaled over time by researchers by **sharing knowledge through storytelling, study visits, and pilot projects**, adapting "best cases" solutions to local contexts, and creating and managing collaboration networks that link local stakeholders and international ones. **New collaborative alliances** across local projects and sectors, including the private sector and grassroot initiatives to collaborate are fundamental for the future of circular cities.

1. Presentations

Prof. Dr. Lina Dagiliene

Kaunas University of Technology

ECLECTIC project

Moderator of the webinar

She moderated the event and managed the interactive session.

Dr. Chiara Pellegrini

Eurac Research

ECLECTIC project

She provided an **overview of the ECLECTIC project**,

presenting the four Living Labs in Coimbra (PT), Bolzano (IT), Jonava (LT) and Gothenburg (SE). The research aims to provide actionable knowledge and to engage local stakeholders in co-selecting measures for the development of CE action plans.

Prof. Leonardo Rosado

Chalmers University of Technology

ECLECTIC project

He introduced the role of **Urban Metabolism Analysis for CE in ECLECTIC**.

He explained the method used for accounting material flows, domestic mass consumption, import and export, industrial production and identify potential opportunities for improving circularity of materials in urban and regional economies.

Mr. Sergio Caetano

CIM-RC

ECLECTIC project

He presented the **experience of Coimbra in collaborating in a research project** to enhance urban and regional circularity.

He focused on the stakeholder engagement process and the value of their insights to prioritize CE measures in the regional CE action plan.

Dr. Carla Rey

University of Turin

CORPUS project

She focused on **participatory methods & civic technologies for circular urban economy used in the CORPUS project** to engage citizens over time in urban renewal processes.

She introduced two Living Labs in Turin & Aigaleo, an open access toolkit and one blockchain-based digital platform for circular urban economies.

Prof. Patrick Zapata

University of Gothenburg

Circular Grassroot project

His presentation "**When grassroots meet governance: puzzles from the field**" highlighted the key role of grassroots organization in conducting CE and sharing economy activities.

Space accessibility is a major issue to enhance their impact and innovative support mechanisms needs to be experimented by cities.

Dr. Jessica Balest

Eurac Research

ECLECTIC project

Her presentation "**What to look at to make circularity just and inclusive?**" showed the qualitative research on the social impact of CE on people and society.

She stressed the need to understand the distribution of benefits and costs associated with CE to ensure that circular transitions in cities are just and inclusive.

2. Interactive Session

The core results of the webinar derive from two rounds of interactive sessions. Participants were engaged in three moderated breakout rooms where they discussed four main questions around research-city collaborations. The four questions were discussed using Mirò boards (Figure 1).

Round 1 – Understanding Roles and Needs

- **Q1. Collaboration needs.** What do cities, local organizations, and researchers need from one another to work in the most impactful way to implement CE solutions?
- **Q2 Conditions for collaboration success.** What conditions need to be fulfilled to foster successful collaboration between cities, researchers, and communities in fostering circular transitions?

Round 2 – Moving towards Impact

- **Q3 Drivers for scalability.** How can we scale local collaboration successes across cities or regions to foster CE?
- **Q4 Innovation in collaborations.** What new alliances or experiments could we try?

Figure 1. Structure of Breakout Rooms

Q1. Collaboration Needs

The discussions revealed that effective collaboration between cities, local organizations, and researchers in implementing circular economy (CE) strategies and solutions depends on several interconnected factors and needs (see Table 1).

Participants underscored the need for **a shared vision and common goals** that unite stakeholders around joint priorities and actions in cities and regions. **Trust, transparency, and mutual understanding** emerged as a fundamental element for lasting partnerships that allow for continuous and committed engagement of stakeholders over time, which is functional to circular urban projects and initiatives.

Another critical need was **knowledge and data sharing** among cities and researchers. This enables informed decision-making, innovation, and mutual learning in new fields where CE demands systemic and real-time tracing of products and materials in local economies.

Sustainable cooperation also requires dedicated **resources and commitment**, including time, personnel, and supportive environments.

Policy and institutional support were recognized as essential for aligning stakeholder priorities and ensuring long-term impact.

Finally, participants underlined that **innovation and local action** are best fostered by encouraging experimentation, embracing learning from failure, and sharing practices was viewed as a key driver for translating ideas into practical, effective CE initiatives.

Table 1. Needs for successful collaboration emerged during Q1 discussion

	Needs	Key Points
1	Shared Vision and Common Goals	Common goals; Shared purpose; Common project; Clear and equally significant benefits; United level of understanding; Common interest and goal; Representation and inclusiveness
2	Trust, Transparency, and Mutual Understanding	Trust; Transparency; Respect; Create a truthful partnership; Listen to each other's needs; Space to fail and adjust; Learn from each partner
3	Knowledge and Data Sharing	Access to city data; Shared information; Knowledge and data; Find a common language among stakeholders; Awareness and communication of the value of collaboration
4	Resources and Commitment	Dedicated time and people; HR; Platforms, spaces, and areas to collaborate; Time; Long-term engagement; Consideration of stakeholders' capacities and resources
5	Policy and Institutional Support	Mandate; Attention and support from local policymakers; Alignment of priorities among stakeholder groups; Supportive frameworks for cooperation
6	Innovation and Local Action	Courage from local businesses to experiment with new solutions; Opportunity to test CE ideas; Step-by-step planning; Exchange of practices; Monitoring of mid- and long-term impact beyond short-term projects

Q2. Conditions for Successful Collaborations

The discussions showed that successful collaboration for fostering circular transitions depends on a mix of regulatory, socio-cultural, and practical conditions (Table 2).

Participants emphasized the importance of **long-term commitment and continuity** noting that collaborations must be sustained over time beyond individual projects and initiatives. Local champions who maintain momentum over time play a crucial role in this process. Continuity must be supported by **regulatory frameworks** that provide clear mandates and policies promoting research-city collaborations. **Space and resources**, including stable funding mechanisms, collaborative platforms, sites for operations and organizational capacity across stakeholders, are necessary to stabilize these collaborations.

Participants also underscored the importance of **raising awareness and motivation** among stakeholders by a shared understanding of mutual needs for CE and demonstrating the benefits of circular solutions. To this end, building **networks on existing relationships** allow cities to strengthen trust and connections, exchange knowledge, and transform participants from passive recipients of research into active contributions through knowledge co-creation and reflection mechanisms.

Effective collaborations towards circular cities require **community ownership** fostered through grassroots engagement and accessible languages to ensure that circular solutions resonate to citizens. Finally, participants highlighted the need for **learning and flexibility**, encouraging experimentation from both successes and failures to strengthen circular transition partnerships over time.

Table 2. Conditions for successful collaborations emerged during Q2 discussion

	Conditions	Key Points
1	Long-Term Commitment	Time; Ongoing participatory processes; Long-term partnerships; Long-term liabilities; Projects as part of long-term roadmaps; Stability and continuity; Existence of champions
2	Regulatory Frameworks	Political will; Clear legislation; Legal and policy frameworks that support collaboration; Mandates; Organizational slack and clarity of roles; Regulations promoting collaboration
3	Space and Resources	Funds; Funding mechanisms to guarantee implementation; Dedicated spaces and human resources; Collaborative digital platforms; Allocation of organizational time and resources;
4	Awareness and Motivation	Awareness; Understanding stakeholders' needs; Motivating by explaining benefits; Connection and feedback loops; Consideration of past mistakes; Track progress on CE
5	Networks on Relationships	Space for partners as active contributors rather than passive receivers; Collaboration built on existing relationships; Feedback and reflection mechanisms
6	Community Ownership	Local ownership; Common language among stakeholders; Local based ownership; Grassroot engagement; Lobby decision-making
7	Learning and Flexibility	Opportunity to test and adapt; Learning from previous experiences; Flexibility to address challenges early rather than reactively; Avoiding stagnation in project phases

Q3. Drivers for Scalability

Beyond needs and enabling conditions, participants identified seven drivers for scaling local CE collaborations from isolated experiments to routinized practices. (see Table 3).

Participants agreed that **communication and dissemination** through storytelling, pilot demonstrations, and intercity learning are crucial to share the circular solutions that work in different contexts and socio-economic sectors. However, rather than copying solutions, successful models should be **adapted to local needs**, capacities, and governance structures.

Exchanges with other cities and participation in international networks linking municipalities and regions across Europe (e.g. DUT, EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, NetZero Cities Network) and international platforms (e.g. Ellen MacArthur Foundation) emerged as an additional driver of mutual learning and scouting of new opportunities in joint projects and initiatives on circularity urban economy. Supportive **policies and dedicated governance structures** that simplify implementation and management in experimenting cross-sectoral circular approaches were also seen as essential to maintain momentum. **Funding and impact assessment** emerged a practical driver, with participants stressing the link between funding and measurement methods to demonstrate impact of research-city collaborations for a CE.

Capacity building across city departments through education, coaching and training programs help improve capabilities for knowledge transfer from research to action. Finally, **the creation of circular markets** can help embed circularity principles into everyday practice and make successful initiatives replicable at broader scales.

Table 3. Drivers for scalability of collaborations emerged during Q3 discussion

	Drivers	Key Points
1	Communication and Dissemination	Storytelling, study visits, and functioning pilots; Dissemination of results; Sharing and presenting experiences; Creating cross-municipal spaces for exchange
2	Adaptation to Local Context	Reflect the needs of the local community; Translate rather than copy local ideas; Develop with local considerations in mind; Adapt successful approaches to new city contexts; Work on what should be adjusted for different conditions
3	Inter-Cities Exchanges	Participation in European and national CE networks; Exchange among neighboring cities; Use project ambassadors; Strengthen city-to-city learning; Using existing city networks;
4	Policies and Governance	Public policies supporting CE scaling; Policy mechanisms that identify and reinforce local success factors; Toolkits and guidelines for replication
5	Funding and Impact Assessment	Dedicated funding; Simple ways to measure CE impact; Additional financial and technical support; Simplified processes and administrative mechanisms to access funds
6	Capacity Building	Education and capacity building; Support through coaching and training; Promote understanding of what makes initiatives transferable
7	Circular Market Development	Circular markets and shopping models; Encouraging replication of successful mechanisms (not just ideas); Using pilot projects as scalable models for new initiatives

Q4. Innovation for Collaborations

Participants expressed a strong interest in developing innovative and experimental alliances bridging research, policy, and local action (see Table 4). They emphasized the value of **cross-institutional** and **cross-sectoral alliances** in driving circular transitions in cities and regions. Examples of these alliances include continuous collaborations among different DUT projects, partnerships among research institutions, municipalities and grassroots actors to test innovative CE approaches across multiple levels and engaging different types of stakeholders, from the private sector to marginalized communities. To this end, **grassroot experimentation** is fundamental to leverage social innovation for circularity and engage marginalized communities

The creation of **resource brokerage systems and digital platforms** was identified as practical step toward connecting resources, opportunities, and expertise across stakeholders to efficiently match demand and supply to solve city challenges in circularity and simplifying access to research knowledge. Participants also highlighted the importance of **replicating and adapting existing tools and pilots** rather than continuously creating new ones to ensure that experiments remain context-specific and scalable.

Finally, **involving new generations**, incorporating spatial, digital, and social dimensions, and demonstrating clear community impact are seen as crucial to enable local innovation ecosystems around circular city transitions.

Table 4. Innovation factors emerging during Q4 discussion

	Innovation factors	Key Points
1	Cross-Institutional and Cross-Sectoral Sectoral Alliances	Between DUT projects; Cross-institutional and cross-sectoral networks; Global alliances; Partnerships with municipalities (e.g., Coimbra collaborating with CIM, IPC); Collaboration between technical and social approaches to circularity
2	Local and Grassroots Experimentation	Projects to test new ideas; Support grassroots experiments and initiatives; Demonstrate clear benefits to communities through pilot projects; Working closely with municipalities to design and implement CE strategies
3	Knowledge Mediation and Resource Platforms	Platforms to match needs, resources, and opportunities; Resource brokerage mechanisms; Publicly available resource "radars" at city or regional levels; Universities as intermediaries between international knowledge and local actions
4	Replication and Adaptation of Existing Models	Test similar concepts in multiple locations with different stakeholders; Recreate existing tools for specific conditions; Explore existing alliances before creating new ones; Adapt and scale proven models to local realities
5	Inclusion and New Dimensions	Involve new generations; Consider spatial, digital, and social dimensions in collaboration and experimentation; Engage communities to co-develop and test new CE strategies

3. Key Insights from Interactive Session

The interactive sessions highlighted several key characteristics of effective research-city collaboration (see Table 5) which help fostering engagement and participation among a wide range of stakeholders. Effective collaboration depends on a combination of structural, social, and knowledge-based characteristics that enable cities, researchers, and local stakeholders to work together over time and keep momentum of activities beyond specific projects.

Participants emphasized that **collaborative governance** forms the foundation of successful research city-collaboration for circular transitions. Building a shared vision, nurturing trust, and establishing clear roles and coordination mechanisms are essential to manage collaborations over time.

A strong **commitment to evidence-based and data-driven action** is equally important to support transparency, informed decision-making, and continuous learning across sectors, departments and units involved in circular transitions. Participants underlined that access to reliable data and **open and user-friendly information flows** allows all stakeholders to track progress, identify challenges, and scale solutions that work from pilot project to structured CE action plans and policies.

Local adaptation and context sensitivity were repeatedly noted as critical. Rather than replicating standard solutions, cities can collaborate with research to translate successful practices into their own socio-economic and cultural settings. This requires **flexible approaches and local engagement** at every stage of research-city collaboration.

The need to **strengthen capacity and knowledge building** was also identified as a priority, needed to establish a common language and enable effective knowledge transfer from research to implementation by city officers. Moreover, innovation and experimentation through pilot projects, living labs, and testing new partnerships, provide practical environments where new ideas can be tested, validated and scaled, while providing additional data and information for measuring impact of collaborations.

Participants further highlighted the role of **scaling and replication** networks which connect local initiatives to regional and European platforms, enabling mutual learning and amplifying the impact of successful experiences.

Finally, **inclusive and intergenerational engagement** emerged as a cross-cutting characteristic for strengthening the impact and potential of research-city collaboration. By bringing together different generations, socioeconomic groups, and community stakeholders in co-creation processes, collaborations can tap into diverse knowledge sources, ensure solutions are contextually relevant, and foster collective ownership that sustains circular initiatives over time.

Table 5. Characteristics of research-cities collaboration emerging from interactive sessions

Characteristics	Description
Collaborative governance	Building a shared vision, trust-based partnerships, and cross-sector coordination between research, policy, and practice
Evidence-based and data-driven action	Promoting data collection, sharing, and impact measurement to support science-informed policymaking.
Local adaptation and context sensitivity	Translating—rather than copying—successful CE models to fit local needs, capacities, and cultural contexts
Capacity and knowledge building	Encouraging peer learning, city-to-city exchanges, and educational programs to strengthen local competencies
Innovation and experimentation	Testing new partnerships, pilot projects, and living labs to co-design scalable circular solutions
Scaling and replication networks	Connecting local initiatives to regional and European platforms to enable replication and shared learning
Inclusive and intergenerational engagement	Involving communities, youth, and marginalized groups to ensure fairness, diversity, and long-term participation

To conclude, the analysis of the results from the interactive sessions pointed to a process for establishing research–city collaboration, which depends on the activation of several interconnected elements:

- **A shared vision and common goals** that unite different stakeholders and encourage joint ownership of CE initiatives.
- **Trust, transparency, and mutual understanding**, built through inclusive dialogue and continuous communication.
- **Open knowledge and data sharing**, ensuring decisions are informed by evidence and collective experience.
- **Dedicated resources, funding, and time** commitments that support continuity beyond short-term projects.
- **Policy and institutional support** to create stable governance structures, mandates, and enabling regulatory frameworks.
- **Encouragement of innovation, experimentation, and local action**, allowing stakeholders to test new ideas and adapt solutions to diverse contexts.
- **Promotion of scaling mechanisms**—such as storytelling, pilot replication, and learning networks—that help local successes spread across regions.
- **Development of new alliances** and cross-sectoral partnerships that connect municipalities, academia, industry, and citizens in co-creating circular solutions.

4. Conclusions and Next steps

Research–city collaboration is a dynamic, multi-level process built on trust, shared vision and goals, and continuous commitment and willingness to pursue them collectively. It flourishes when partners share knowledge, communicate openly, and are supported by stable policies, governance structures and resources that provide space and legitimacy to their explorative actions towards circular transitions. Encouraging innovation ecosystems to enhance the creation of productive relations among researchers, cities and the private sector, involving grassroots organizations to leverage bottom-up social innovation, promoting cross-sector and cross-institutional learning at local and international levels helps scale promising circular solutions and drive urban transformations in ways that are systemic and recognized by the stakeholders that integrate them in their daily lives.

This webinar has been a first attempt by the ECLECTIC project team to promote research-city collaboration by i) creating synergies with the CORPUS and CIRCULAR GRASSROOT projects to share the experiences, approaches and methods for working together with stakeholders on circular urban transitions; ii) engaging city representatives, local associations and other researchers to understand the needs, conditions, drivers and innovative factors supporting effective collaboration for building circular solutions that are systemic, durable and adapt to local contexts while addressing international challenges.

The authors hope that this report will support researchers and municipal authorities in developing collaborative frameworks that acknowledge and address the key points emerged during the workshop, enabling the implementation of processes that can contribute to sustainable and circular futures in urban and regional context.

About the Projects

CIRCULAR GRASSROOTS

Enabling CircuLar Economy aCTIon plans for small and medium-sized Cities

[ECLECTIC](#) aims to support small and mid-sized cities and regions in designing, implementing and monitoring tailored CE action plans that enhance resource efficiency and minimize environmental impact. A key focus is on understanding urban metabolism and material flows to inform decisions, while also ensuring that marginalized social groups are not left behind in the transition.

Phygital Cooperation in Retrofitting Public Space

The main challenge addressed by the [CORPUS](#) project is the revival of degraded public spaces in peripheral urban neighbourhoods, whereas "revival" means both material renovation and socio-economic regeneration. We aim at studying how participatory and digitally enabled circular urban economies (CUE) can support citizens in collectively designing and realizing sharing and circular practices in their daily spaces.

Circular Grassroots Innovations for Sustainable and Inclusive Urban Transitions

[CIRCULAR GRASSROOTS](#) aims at examining the challenges and opportunities that urban circular grassroots initiatives encounter to create, maintain and scale their solutions for sustainable and inclusive transitions from below. It investigates these challenges and opportunities in terms of a) space, b) collaborative and democratic arenas among local government, urban planners and grassroots organizations, c) inclusivity and scalability of the grassroots.

About the DUT Partnership

The Driving Urban Transitions (DUT) Partnership to a sustainable future is an intergovernmental research and innovation programme addressing key challenges of urban transitions. A public-public partnership to facilitate an innovation ecosystem for urban transitions. The DUT Partnership is co-funded within the European Research and Innovation (R&I) Framework Programme, Horizon Europe. The partnership started in 2022, building upon and stepping up the ambition and efforts of the Joint Programming Initiative (JPI) Urban Europe.

About the Authors

The report and the workshop were organized by the researchers of the ECLECTIC project in collaboration with the researchers of the CORPUS and CIRCULAR GRASSROOT projects.

Prof. Dr. Jurgita Bruneckienė

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She is a full professor and a researcher in the Circular Economy Research Group. She has extensive experience in participating in and leading research projects on circular economy impact measurement, the role of municipalities in circular economy implementation, and industrial behavior toward circular economy practices.

Dr. Chiara Pellegrini

Eurac Research

ECLECTIC project

She is Senior Researcher at Eurac Institute for Renewable Energy. She is project manager of the ECLECTIC project, focusing on energy, circular economy, and policies and governance of innovation and sustainability.

Dr. Carla Rey

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CORPUS project

She is a Researcher in the Territories and Digital Communities research unit of the Social Computing group of the Department of Computer Science at the University of Turin. She has extensive experience with local authorities and is a UNDP consultant on SDG local action and visualizing innovation in cities.

Appendix 1: Mirò Boards

Figure 2. Results from Breakout Room n°1

Round 1 : Understanding Roles and Needs (20 min)

Round 2 : Moving towards Impact (15 min)

Figure 3. Results from Breakout Room n°2

Round 1 : Understanding Roles and Needs (20 min)

processes which take into consideration different abilities, ways of working, time lines

Q1: What do cities, local organizations, and researchers need from one another to collaborate effectively to implement CE solutions?

- time
- Clear and equally significant benefits
- Unified level of understanding
- Common interest and goal
- Human resources
- platforms, spaces, areas, to collaborate
- Mandate
- Long-term liabilities
- Clear legislation
- Political will
- funding

Q2: What conditions need to be fulfilled to foster successful collaboration between cities, researchers, and communities in fostering circular transitions?

- Stability, and an understanding that cities are often the unstable part
- Outcome is a result of how it's organized, that has to be dealt with early, and chosen rather than "happened"
- Motivating by explaining the benefits
- Organizational slack and mandate
- An idea about what to do with them, to not get stuck in procrastination problems
- Give all partners space to partners, rather than as passive receivers

Round 2 : Moving towards Impact (15 min)

Q3: How can we scale local successes across cities or regions to foster CE?

- storytelling, study visits, functioning pilots
- Reflect the needs of the local community
- Collaboration with the municipality
- Pioneers are needed. Nearly already other city 1 has done something, city 2 dares to - no networks to spread knowledge
- Use pilot projects already implemented
- By not copying them, but to translate them to other local context.
- Large cities could just help smaller ones by taking care of their materials which are in small volume
- Developing with local considerations in mind
- Before implementing an initiative, it is necessary to educate the community.
- The cities can scale up, down perhaps approach the others on the same level

Q4: What new alliances or experiments could we try?

- a tool should be recreated for specific conditions
- test the same thing in several places but with different stakeholders
- Resource brokerage
- Publicly available resource "radar" at the regional or city level.
- Not so sure about the NEW, perhaps finding about already working alliances and forms, before inventing new. Much as already "out there", find it
- Demonstrate clear benefits to communities through pilot projects or initiatives.

Figure 4. Results from Breakout Room n°3

CIRCULAR GRASSROOTS

Driving Urban
Transitions

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the European Union